

Effects of organic groups grafted carbon nanotube on tensile creep behavior of CNTs/epoxy nano-composites

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Abstract

In this paper, dog bone shaped specimens of epoxy as well as CNTs/epoxy nano-composites (NC) were prepared and examined to determine effects of CNTs contents and their surface organic groups on tensile creep properties. Experimental results show that the embedded CNTs significantly reduced the initial strain of the epoxy resin due to modulus increase of the CNTs/epoxy composite. Under the same stress level of loading, amino group grafted CNTs/epoxy showed the least strain compared with the neat epoxy resin and pristine CNTs/epoxy. With an addition of 0.5 phr amino-CNTs, the pure creep strain of the amino-CNTs/epoxy at room temperature was decreased by 26.8 % compared to the neat epoxy resin. Besides, the creep rate of the amino-CNTs/epoxy specimens was much lower than that of the neat epoxy resin. On the contrary, the same amount of pristine CNTs embedded into the epoxy resin increased the pure creep strain by 10.7 %.

1 Introduction

Due to their advantage in weight reduction of structures, fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites (FRP) have been widely used in the past decades. However, low creep resistance of FRP remains a puzzling problem to be solved. Creep is the time-dependent continued deformation of a material under a persistent load which is usually significantly lower than the yield stress of the material. Materials with high creep resistance are critical in long-term structural applications to ensure dimensional stability and load-carrying capability. Generally, fibers in FRP composites have high modulus and consequently negligible creep deformation, while polymer matrixes show much greater creep owing to their flexible molecular structure. Therefore, it is reasonable to focus on enhancing the creep resistance of the polymer matrix.

Numerous researches have varified that creep of polymer matrix can be effectively reduced by involved stiff fillers^[1-7]. As shown in several experimental and theoretical researches, dynamic behavior of polymers is strongly affected by the boundary effect of the involved nano-particles which have huge specific surface area and dimension similar to polymer chains^[8-11]. With excellent mechanical properties such as high specific strength, high specific modulus and great length-to-diameter ratio, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are promising to enhance the creep resistance of polymers significantly.

Zhang et al.^[12] investigated creep mitigation effects of CNTs on creep resistance of polymers. They found that single-walled CNTs in low weight fractions (0.1–0.25%) are effective in limiting the load-induced re-orientation of epoxy chains, resulting in a significant slowing of the creep response. On the contrary, creep strain of epoxy resin increased when weight fraction of CNTs reached 1%, resulting from aggregation of CNTs.

Tehrani et al.^[13] found that the improvements in the creep properties of CNTs/epoxy composites were not as high as anticipated through mixture rule using nano-indentation. The reduction effect of 3 wt. % CNTs on creep response was more significant at lower load and higher temperature. Starkova et al.^[14] studied creep and recovery behavior of CNTs/epoxy resin composites using the same method. The effect of CNTs content was negligible and the incorporation of CNTs brought no negative effect on creep and recovery property of commercial epoxy resin.

Despite that a few researches have studied the effect of CNTs on creep behavior of thermosetting polymer matrixes, the role of CNTs and effect of CNTs-polymer interface are rarely reported. In this paper, CNTs were used as filler to improve creep property of epoxy resin. The aim of the present study is to investigate effects of CNTs contents and surface groups on tensile creep property of CNTs/epoxy composites, and evaluate the role of CNTs and CNTs-epoxy interface in the creep response reduction of epoxy resin.

2 Experimental details

2.1 Materials

As a matrix polymer for FRP, a commercially available epoxy system CYD-128/DDM (Sinopec asset management co., Ltd, China) was used. The choice of the epoxy system for this study was influenced by its wide use in conventional fiber reinforced composites. As shown in Fig.1, multi-walled CNTs with length of 8-15 μ m and diameter of 50 nm (Chengdu organic chemicals Ltd, China) were dispersed by tip sonication in acetone for 1 h and mixed with epoxy resin. Then the mixture was dispersed by tip sonication for 2 h and by high speed shearing for 1 h. After that, DDM was dissolved in acetone and added to the CNTs-epoxy-acetone mixture, followed by degassing, casting and curing. CNTs/epoxy specimens for tensile test and dynamic mechanical analysis (sample size: 2.5 \times 4 \times 30 mm³) with different kind of CNTs (pristine, amino, carboxyl and hydroxyl CNTs) and varied amino-CNTs weight fraction (0.25%, 0.5%, 0.75% and 1%) were obtained. Specimens with pristine, carboxylic, amino, hydroxyl CNTs are denoted as P, C, A, H, respectively. And the following figure denotes contents of CNTs added per hundreds of resin (phr).

Fig. 1 Preparation of CNTs/epoxy specimens for tensile and DMTA tests

2.2 Tensile tests

The uniaxial tensile tests were performed on a CMT5105 universal testing machine. The tests were performed at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min under room temperature according to GB/T 1004.4-2006. Elongation of the samples was measured using an extensometer with a gauge length of 50 mm. Elastic modulus was determined in the elastic range of strains 0.05–0.25%. Repeatability of the data was checked for three to five duplicate samples.

2.3 Tensile creep tests

Uniaxial tensile creep tests were performed on a GWT1104 test machine (ratio of the arms 1:40) according to GB/T 11546.1-2008 for 10 h under 20 MPa. Elongation of the specimens was obtained by averaging values of two strain gauge extensometers with span lengths of 50 mm with accuracy of 0.001mm.

2.4 Thermal analysis

Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) was carried out to determine the effects of nanotubes on glass transition temperature (T_g). The DMTA experiments were performed with bar samples in a PerkinElmer device of DMA8000. The measurements were carried out in single-cantilever bending mode (deflection of 0.5 mm) at a frequency of 1 Hz from 25 $^{\circ}$ C to 150 $^{\circ}$ C at a heating rate of 2 $^{\circ}$ C per min. T_g was determined from the mechanical loss factor ($\tan \delta$) for at least two samples of each material produced.

3 Results and discussion

As we all know, macro properties of nano-composites are closely related to their micro structures. Due to their high free surface energy, even well dispersed nano-fillers naturally aggregate to form clusters. The large-scale aggregated character of nano-scale fillers is a big obstacle in nano-composite technology and perceived as the most important factor that compromises nano-composites mechanical performance^[15, 16].

The storage modulus vs. temperature and $\tan \delta$ vs. temperature curves of the CNTs/epoxy composites are shown in Fig. 2. Compared to neat epoxy resin, storage modulus of CNTs/epoxy composites tended to decrease significantly at lower temperature. Correspondingly, T_g of CNTs/epoxy composites, defined by the temperatures at the peak of $\tan \delta$ curves, were much lower than that of the neat epoxy resin. Among the nano-composites, amino CNTs/epoxy composite show the highest T_g , probably because that amino groups on CNTs surface improved dispersion of CNTs in the epoxy resin and could react with the epoxy resin.

Despite that a great deal study on CNTs/epoxy composites has been conducted, effects of CNTs on T_g of epoxy resin was still controversial. Varied CNTs properties (diameter, length, manufacture method and producer) and epoxy systems complicate the comparison work. As pointed by Allaoui et al.^[17], T_g of multi-walled CNTs/epoxy were scattered and no clear trend appeared. There are some reasons for degradation of T_g of epoxy resin with CNTs fillers. Liao et al.^[18] showed that the use of solvent in the fabrication process can lead to a large decrease of the T_g . Besides, the introduction of CNTs increased significantly the viscosity of the mixture, which is expected to decrease the cure of epoxy resin in the diffusion-controlled stage at the end of curing.

Fig. 2 Effect of organic groups on CNTs on storage modulus and tan loss angles of NC

The determined Young's modulus and tensile strength for the neat epoxy and CNTs/epoxy composites are shown in Fig. 3. The tensile modulus of all of the CNTs/epoxy composite specimens was least 9% higher than that of the neat epoxy resin with limited standard errors. Specially, hydroxyl-CNTs/epoxy specimens had the highest average modulus. In terms of average tensile strength, carboxylic-CNTs/epoxy composite was the highest, though the standard errors were not negligible. Average tensile strength of functionalized CNTs/epoxy composite specimens was higher than that of the neat epoxy resin. On the contrary, average tensile strength of the pristine CNTs/epoxy specimens was lower than that of the neat epoxy resin, resulting from chemical inertia of the pristine CNTs and consequently weak interface between the pristine CNTs and the epoxy resin.

Fig. 3 Effect of organic groups on CNTs on tensile strength and modulus of NC

With both acceptable T_g and tensile modulus, the amino-CNTs/epoxy composites were chosen to study effects of contents of the CNTs on static tension property and tensile creep property of the amino-CNTs/epoxy composites. As shown in Fig. 4, the tensile modulus of the amino-CNTs/epoxy composite specimens was about 10% higher than that of the neat epoxy resin, and was not susceptible to the contents of the CNTs. Tensile strength of the CNTs/epoxy composite specimens increased slightly as contents of CNTs increased, but decreased when the content reached 0.75 phr due to aggregation of the CNTs.

Fig. 4 Effect of contents of amino-CNTs on tensile strength and modulus of NC

Representative creep and creep strain vs. time curves of specimens with the pristine CNTs and amino-CNTs and various contents under 20 MPa are shown in Fig. 5. Apparently initial strain contributed over 80% of total strain in loading duration of 10 h. The involvement of both type of CNTs significantly reduced the initial strain of the epoxy resin due to an increase of modulus of the CNT/epoxy composite. A0.5 showed the least strain above all of the specimens. The inserted figure in Fig. 5 offered a clear outline of the effects of CNTs on pure creep strain. With an addition of 0.5 phr amino-CNTs, the pure creep strain of the CNT/epoxy

composite at room temperature was decreased by 26.8 % compared to the neat epoxy resin. On the contrary, the same amount of pristine CNTs embedded into the epoxy resin increased the pure creep strain by 10.7 % .

In order to investigate creep law of the specimens and to eliminate the error induced by data fluctuation, the pure creep strain scatters were fitted by a power model. Creep rates of the specimens were calculated and plotted according to power model, and shown in Fig. 6. Obviously, the power model fits well with the experimental data. As the simulated creep rate versus time curves indicated, when content of the amino-CNTs is less than 1% the creep rate of CNTs/epoxy composite specimens with amino-CNTs was much lower than that of the neat epoxy resin.

Fig. 5 Total strain and pure creep strain of specimens

Fig. 6 Pure creep strain and pure creep strain rate of three specimens (solid lines: fitting curves of pure creep strain, dotted lines: pure creep strain curves calculated according to power model)

Pure creep strain vs. time curves of CNTs/epoxy specimens with various contents of amino-CNTs were shown in Fig. 7. Pure creep strain of amino-CNTs/epoxy composite specimens was significantly lower than that of the epoxy resin, except for specimens with 1 phr CNTs. Pure creep strain curves of the amino-

CNTs/epoxy composite with CNTs contents of 0.75 phr and below are close, and pure creep strain curve of A0.5 is slightly lower. Due to aggregation of the CNTs at higher contents, pure creep of the epoxy resin cannot be further reduced by increasing contents of the CNTs, as shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7 Pure creep strain ϵ of amino-CNTs/epoxy composite specimens

Fig. 8 Aggregation of amino-CNTs in nano-composite specimens with CNTs content of 1 phr

According to the experimental results in this paper, mechanical property of CNTs could be made good use of when they are isolate. The interface between CNTs and epoxy resin plays an important role in coordinating strain and transferring stress to CNTs, which act as micro pins in the matrix. However, large-scale clusters of the CNTs act as defects in the composites and decrease creep resistance and T_g of the epoxy resin.

4 Conclusions

Incorporation of CNTs with different surface groups contributed significant increase on elastic modulus and resulting creep resistance of epoxy resin, whereas addition of CNTs decreased T_g of the CNTs/epoxy composites. Addition of 0.5 phr amino-CNTs decreased both pure creep strain and creep rate of the CNTs/epoxy composites, while pristine CNTs showed the opposite effects. When content of amino-CNTs is lower than 0.75 phr, pure creep strain of the amino-CNTs/epoxy composite specimens has limited difference.

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